

SOCIAL SCIENCES, HUMANITIES AND ARTS

Traumatic mortality in late human evolution from an integrated non-invasive bioarchaeological and taphonomic perspective

Traumatic death affects our daily life, but how did traumatic mortality affect human behaviour from an evolutionary perspective? TRAUMOBITA aims to understand how traumatic mortality among prehistoric humans shaped our behaviour during the Late Pleistocene to the Middle Holocene. Confirming that how we died had an enormous influence on our ancestors and represents an enormous change in how we understand human societies. Traumatic mortality has an enormous influence among non-human primate social life and environmental adaptations, but not much effort has been dedicated to the study of how such deaths affected the behavioural development of modern humans. Identifying and understanding how humans died is essential for determining the role of violence in shaping our behaviour and, it seems, an equally important factor among our primate relatives. The goal here is to study these behavioural adaptations on the basis of two analytical sections. The first will comprise analysis of human fossils from different key sites from Lake Turkana (Africa): the region is known as the cradle of humankind and the archaeopaleontological record is an essential one for reconstructing our own evolutionary path. The second will be dedicated to the integration of forensic science into taphonomic study of human fossils, in addition to the development of new non-invasive methods based on virtual analysis and experimentation. The data obtained from this approach will facilitate the identification and the characterisation of traumatic mortality in the archaeological record, in order to integrate our results into the study of past societies to determine which behavioural changes are related to traumatic mortality. The research is an integrated analysis that guarantees the interdisciplinary and innovative nature of the project. Little is known on the role of traumatic mortality in human behavioural adaptations, and therefore the project will represent a major advance.

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The research: Scope, objectives and hypothesis

Mortality is a major fact in evolution and ecology, and the timing and causes of death can drive many aspects of adaptation. In prehistoric hunter-gatherer societies the relation between resource availability and disease, particularly in childhood, has been seen as a major mortality parameter. However, there is increasing evidence in the archaeological record and among non-human primates that traumatic causes of death (i.e. predation, accidents and inter- and intra-specific violence) play a significant role in demography and adaptive response during our late evolution. The aim of TRAUMOBITA is to understand how such traumatic deaths among prehistoric humans shaped our behaviour, and to answer the following research questions: i) How can traumatic mortality be characterized? ii) Why did traumatic mortality occur? iii) Does traumatic mortality change according to social and environmental change? and iv) Did traumatic mortality affect human behavioural adaptations?

A challenging hypothesis would be that traumatic mortality caused by inter- and intra-specific predation and violence is a major evolutionary factor in human evolution shaping modern and complex behaviours. Focusing on a range of sites across Lake Turkana (Kenya) (Figure 1), TRAUMOBITA aims to investigate traumatic mortality among prehistoric hunter-gatherers from East Africa and answer these questions. An exceptional sample of human fossils dating from the Late Pleistocene to the Holocene will be analysed from a bioarchaeological and taphonomic non-invasive perspective, linking archaeology and forensic science, to understand the role and factors of traumatic mortality in prehistoric human behavioural adaptations.

Little is known about this among past societies and the proposed research will represent a major advance in our understanding of the role of violent death in late human evolution.

Why Lake Turkana?

West Turkana, Kenya, is one of the key regions for answering questions regarding the late evolution of human universal characters and major behavioural adaptation events of *Homo sapiens*, our species (1). For instance, clear evidence of inter-personal/group conflict and violence has been inferred among hunter-gatherers at Nataruk (Kenya) during the early Holocene (2) (Figure 2). In this sense, other sites in West Turkana dating from 50,000 to 10,000 years ago (late Pleistocene to early Holocene) have enormous potential for providing insights about the behavioural context of the emergence of modernity.

Evidence of bone injury

skull embedded projectile

1) Foley et al. (2016) Major transitions in human evolution. *Phil Trans R Soc B* 371: 20150229.
2) Mirazón-Lahr et al. (2016) Inter-group violence among early Holocene hunter-gatherers of West Turkana. *Nature* 529: 394-398.

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